

Confirmation of the occurrence of *Anaspis maculata* (GEOFFROY in FOURCROY, 1885) (Coleoptera: Scrapytiidae) in Poland

Potwierdzenie występowania *Anaspis maculata* (GEOFFROY in FOURCROY, 1885) (Coleoptera: Scrapytiidae) w Polsce

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ABSTRACT. The occurrence of *Anaspis maculata* in Poland is confirmed with new findings in Baltic Coast and Pomeranian Lake District.

KEY WORDS: Tenebrionoidea, new records, Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve.

Scrapytiidae recorded from Poland include 19 species of *Anaspis* GEOFFROY, 1762, a single species of *Cyratanaspis* EMERY, 1876, and two species of *Scrapytia* LATREILLE, 1807 (KUBISZ 2006, KUBISZ et al. 2014, GRZYWOCZ 2022). *Anaspis*, the most speciose genus among the Polish members of the family, includes species that were recorded a long time ago based on just a few findings, and their presence in the Polish fauna requires confirmation with new data. One such species is *Anaspis maculata* (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. *Anaspis maculata*, a specimen collected in the vicinity of the Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve, photo R. RUTA.

Ryc. 1. *Anaspis maculata*, okaz zebrany w pobliżu rez. Sławieńskie Dęby, fot. R. RUTA.

The geographical range of *Anaspis maculata* extends from England and western Scandinavia to the Mediterranean, and the easternmost localities are in Poland and Hungary (KUBISZ 2006). In Poland, *A. maculata* was collected in Białowieża in the 1870s or 1880s by WRÓBLEWSKI and in Warsaw-Gocławek in 1863 by OSTERLOFF (1885). A record from Puławy (TENENBAUM 1929) was based on the erroneous identification of *Anaspis thoracica* (KUBISZ et al. 2014). As this species was not found again in Poland after the 1880s, its existence in Poland seemed doubtful and was classified as ‘probably extinct’ (EX?) on the Polish red list of beetles (PAWŁOWSKI et al. 2002). KUBISZ (2006) suggested that if the species did still occur in Poland, it would most likely be found in the western part of the country.

During field studies conducted in NW Poland, a new locality of this species was indeed found:

- Pomeranian Lake District: Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve (UTM: XA02), 336b forest section, 11 V 2024, 1 ex. on flowers of *Cardamine amara* L. in a small, slow-flowing stream in a well-preserved deciduous forest, leg. R. RUTA; vicinity of Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve, E edge of 338a f. sec., 11 V 2024, 1 ex. on flowers of *Cardamine amara* in a small, slow-flowing stream (Fig. 2), S edge of 312b f. sec., N edge of 337a f. sec., S from 336b f. sec., 8 VI 2024, numerous individuals on flowers of *Filipendula ulmaria* (L.) MAXIM (Fig. 3) and *Sambucus nigra* L. leg. & coll. R. RUTA.

Fig. 2. Habitat of *Anaspis maculata* in the vicinity of the Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve, 11 V 2024, photo R. RUTA.

Ryc. 2. Środowisko występowania *Anaspis maculata* w pobliżu rez. Sławieńskie Dęby, 11 V 2024, fot. R. RUTA.

Fig. 3. *Anaspis maculata* on flowers of *Filipendula ulmaria* in the vicinity of the Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve, 8 VI 2024, photo R. RUTA.

Ryc. 3. *Anaspis maculata* na kwiatostanie wiązówki błotnej *Filipendula ulmaria* w pobliżu rez. Sławieńskie Dęby, 8 VI 2024, fot. R. RUTA.

Another specimen of this species was found in the collection of the Upper Silesian Museum in Bytom:
– Baltic Coast: Międzyzdroje (VV67), 26 V 2003, 1 ex., leg. & det. H. SZOŁTYS.

The Sławieńskie Dęby nature reserve protects a small patch of a well-preserved, old-growth forest, a mosaic of oak-hornbeam and riparian forests. As the areas adjacent to the nature reserve are of equally significant natural value (confirmed *inter alia* by the presence of *A. maculata* in both the reserve and its vicinity), enlargement of the nature reserve should be considered.

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REFERENCES

- GRZYWOCZ J. 2022. *Scraptia testacea* ALLEN, 1940 (Coleoptera: Scruptiidae: Scruptiinae) – nowy gatunek chrząszcza w koleopterofaunie Polski. *Acta Entomologica Silesiana*, **30** (online 024): 1-3.
- KUBISZ D. 2006. Oedemeridae i Scruptiidae Polski (Coleoptera, Tenebrionoidea). *Monografie Faunistyczne*, 24: 1-165.
- KUBISZ D., IWAN D., TYKARSKI P. 2014. Tenebrionoidea: Tetratomidae, Melandryidae, Ripiphoridae, Prostomidae, Oedemeridae, Mycteridae, Pythidae, Aderidae, Scruptiidae. Critical checklist, distribution in Poland and meta-analysis. *Coleoptera Poloniae*, Vol. 2. University of Warsaw – Faculty of Biology, Natura oprima dux Foundation, Warszawa. 470 pp.
- OSTERLOFF F. 1885. O chrząszczach krajowych. Dalszy ciąg. *Pamiętnik Fizyograficzny*, **5**: 202-215.
- PAWŁOWSKI J., KUBISZ D., MAZUR M. 2002. Coleoptera chrząszcze. (ss. 88-110) [In:] Z. GŁOWACIŃSKI (ed.). *Czerwona lista zwierząt ginących i zagrożonych w Polsce*. IOP PAN, Kraków. 155 pp.
- TENENBAUM SZ. 1929. Nowe dla Polski gatunki i odmiany chrząszczy. IV. *Polskie Pismo Entomologiczne*, **7**: 188-192.

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